

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION OF LABOR IN CHILDREN OF OLDER PRESCHOOL AGE

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the problem of education of labor in children of senior preschool age as an important quality in the system of moral values of the society, which is formed in the conditions of labor activity. The urgency of the problem is due to the insufficient study of this issue in preschool pedagogy.

Key words: educational process, pedagogical technologies, senior preschool age, diligence, labor activity.

Introduction. The current century is the era of global political, economic and social transformations in society, which entails an urgent need for the development of a person who is ready for labor effort, creative self-realization and social activity throughout life. A person with these qualities can be called competitive, only such a person can achieve high results in his activities.

The problem of educating a positive attitude to work or diligence has again become relevant today due to the increasing role of activity and initiative of preschoolers in the educational process, the need to create conditions for self-realization of the individual [1, 2]. Introduction to work from an early age develops in children such qualities as independence, organization, activity, initiative, perseverance, diligence. Labor forms the child, promotes self-determination and development of all spheres of personality. For modern science, the issue of the development of industriousness in preschool age is one of the most relevant. In the

latest developments, we are talking about the need to educate a positive attitude of children to work, which in essence is diligence [3, 4, 5].

The upbringing of the industriousness of preschoolers is, in our opinion, the most important component in the work of kindergarten teachers. Labor activity has been assigned its place in the pedagogical process of the kindergarten, its program has been defined, pedagogical conditions and technologies have been developed [6, 7]. Work, as you know, is one of the main means of versatile education of the individual. In the course of labor activity, the personality of a preschooler, his relationships with other children, independence and self-esteem, and a value attitude towards the environment as a result of labor are formed. Diligence, being one of the most important moral qualities, is associated with the development of other morally valuable skills and behavioral habits. The pedagogical meaning of educating industriousness lies in the fact that, together with instilling the desire to work, children develop moral motives that stimulate labor activity, in particular, the desire for creative activity as a person's life position in the future [8, 9, 10].

Diligence as a personality trait should be considered in the unity of four components: cognitive, emotional, personal and behavioral [11, 12]. The cognitive component is the presence of ideas about labor, labor processes and professions, an understanding of the need and social significance of labor. The emotional component is interest in labor activity, desire to work, satisfaction from the process and result of labor. The personal component includes the manifestation of the qualities of activity, initiative, independence, accuracy, perseverance, responsibility, creativity. The behavioral component of industriousness includes the formation of practical skills: the ability to plan, mastery of work skills, the ability to adequately evaluate the results of work, and exercise self-control [13, 14].

The process of labor education of children should be focused on ensuring that children understand the meaning of work, its necessity and benefit for

themselves or others. This is one of the main conditions for the education of industriousness.

One of the promising approaches to the organization of child labor and the education of industriousness today is the technology of “entering the child into real labor relations” by M. V. Krulekht. Its distinguishing feature is the design of the pedagogical process, which is focused on the phased process of forming a preschooler as a subject of activity. The organization of the educational process based on the integration of means of labor education determines the algorithm for introducing a preschooler to the modern world in the context of different types of children's activities. According to the technology of M. V. Krulekht, the initial stage of acquaintance with the modern world is expressed in the process of accumulating information about the surrounding objects and the work activity of the elders. So, at a younger age, this is carried out through observation of the process of creating various products (handicrafts, buildings) by adults; in middle preschool age with children, they organize observations of the work of employees of a preschool organization; older preschoolers are interested in the professional activities of their parents, their homework and hobbies.

The second stage is characterized by the acquisition of such skills as the regulation of one's actions and the ability to evaluate them. So, in the younger group, children learn to serve themselves, to satisfy their needs on their own; in the middle group, preschoolers learn the skills of setting the table and washing toy dishes; at an older age, children should learn how to clean the house with a vacuum cleaner, learn how to sew on a button, and cook basic dishes.

The third stage is connected with the establishment of relationships between the preschooler and others in the labor process. To implement this stage in the group, it is necessary to equip a subject-spatial environment that takes into account the age of the pupils, their gender, interests, abilities and hobbies. For kids, important bright didactic aids that contribute to learning the ability to fasten

buttons and lace up. In the group of older preschoolers, it is necessary to provide centers for children's creativity with equipment for boys and girls.

At the age of 4-5 years, preschoolers can already independently identify certain goals and achieve them, but they lack the skills to plan their own activities. At an older age, preschoolers develop the habit of completing the work they have begun to the end, as well as the ability to act together with their peers, negotiate, help, and be responsible for the assigned work together. The teacher stimulates in preschoolers the interest in the work of parents, kindergarten employees and surrounding adults, at the same time expanding their general horizons and enriching the active vocabulary. Children are led to realize the importance of a person's activity in a particular profession, thereby solving the problems of early career guidance and positive socialization. The educator conducts conversations during which he brings up respect for the work of adults, the working person, shows the social significance of the products of labor, introduces the world of modern professions that have a clear and significant result. The teacher leads to the understanding that different types of professions can be interconnected.

The teacher introduces children to works of fiction and organizes didactic games that enrich ideas about work and people of work. One of the tasks of the teacher is to support in children the desire for self-service, the desire and willingness to work, the formation of practical skills and abilities. These aspects find their solution in the application of playing techniques, regular exercises and monitoring of children's activities. A positive assessment of the work of a preschooler, and especially a reward for excellent results of work, is a good motivation for a child.

Household work becomes an important aspect of a child's life in kindergarten. This type of labor activity should be organized in the form of various assignments and exciting tasks for the child. They allow you to gradually arouse interest in the labor process. The most effective methods of educating industriousness are considered to be the interaction between a child and an adult,

encouragement and game techniques. Joint labor activity with an adult (teacher, parents, janitor) evokes positive emotions in a preschooler, actualizes interest and desire to work together. In the course of joint activities, adults need to give preschoolers a clear example of diligence, responsibility, and positive relationships with each other.

In older preschoolers, it is necessary to educate a value attitude towards the results of labor, both one's own and others. So, if a preschooler glued a book, then he not only tries to handle it carefully, but also encourages his peers to do this. At the senior preschool age, children get acquainted with the work activities of adults through walks and excursions outside the kindergarten, classes, meetings. The example of the older generation, in our opinion, plays an important role for preschool children, they learn to respect things, nature. At this age stage, it is possible to use an indirect way of getting acquainted with the labor of adults: watching filmstrips, videos, reading fiction, stories of the educator about the labor exploits of the people. Didactic games will be an effective way to consolidate the material covered.

In order for children's labor to really become a means of moral education, in parallel with the development of labor skills and abilities, it is necessary to direct the preschooler's efforts to work that will be useful for the entire children's team, in which satisfaction from the results of one's own work for others is manifested, awareness of the significance of one's relationships with peers. In the course of work, friendships, mutual assistance and mutual assistance develop between children. Business relations are born, the ability to jointly plan work, fairly distribute the volume, a responsible attitude to work, that is, in the course of work, the mastered rules of a culture of behavior are fixed.

When organizing role-playing games, it is important to create conditions for the inclusion of familiar labor processes with real tools in a conditional game plot. At the same time, it is necessary to widely apply in practice techniques that encourage the creative development of the idea, an independent search for the

materials necessary for the implementation of the game plot (substitute objects, imaginary objects).

A new direction has appeared in the content of modern preschool education - economic education, which involves propaedeutic work with children to study the main economic categories and cultivate a careful attitude to objects and resources. The economic education of preschoolers, as part of moral and labor education, involves the study by children of the basics of financial literacy, such categories as labor, product, cost, expenses - income, goods, budget, the formation of the qualities of a reasonable consumer (rationality, thrift, frugality, reasonableness, prudence).

Conclusions. So, labor activity has a deep moral context: preschoolers realize that their work, the result of their work is necessary for someone, pleasant for someone and causes a feeling of gratitude, this stimulates the development of the desire to work and industriousness. Such emotional support for the result of child labor is its main pedagogical value. Children's own labor should be considered the most important means of instilling industriousness. Formed labor skills and abilities are the basis for cultivating the habit of work and readiness to perform work, a positive assessment of labor activity.

References:

1. Mamasaxatovna, Y. F. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachining innovasion faoliyatini shakllantirish shartlari. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(1), 134-137.
2. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2019). Психологические механизмы воздействия игры на младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 240-243.
3. Mamasakhatovna, Y. F. (2022). Application of Interactive Board in Teaching Preschool Children. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 79-83.
4. Mamasakhatovna, Y. F. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*.

5. Юлдошева, Ф. М., & Избосарова, З. А. (2018). Особенности развития творческих способностей в дошкольном возрасте. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 117-118.
6. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Чувства и этические представления дошкольника. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-1), 434-436.
7. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Взаимосвязь проблем воспитания познавательного интереса и развития мышления в процессе обучения математике. *Вопросы педагогики*, (6-1), 348-351.
8. Yuldosheva Feruza Mamasaxatovna. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'limda steam ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish zaruriyati. *Journal of new century innovations*, 2(1), 170–177.
9. Турдимуродов, Д. (2023). Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida qat'iyatlilik sifatini jismoniy tarbiya darslarida tarbiyalash. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 218-223.
10. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.
11. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. *In International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).
12. Yuldashevich TD. Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. Problems and scientific solutions, Australia, Melbourne.
13. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Peculiarities of Volitional Qualities in Physical Education of Schoolchildren. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(2), 217-220.

14. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.